

On an additive analogue of the function S

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The function S , and its dual S_* are defined by

$$S(n) = \min\{m \in \mathbb{N} : n|m!\};$$

$$S_*(n) = \max\{m \in \mathbb{N} : m!|n\} \quad (\text{see e.g. [1]})$$

We now define the following "additive analogue", which is defined on a subset of real numbers.

Let

$$S(x) = \min\{m \in \mathbb{N} : x \leq m!\}, \quad x \in (1, \infty) \quad (1)$$

as well as, its dual

$$S_*(x) = \max\{m \in \mathbb{N} : m! \leq x\}, \quad x \in [1, \infty). \quad (2)$$

Clearly, $S(x) = m$ if $x \in ((m-1)!, m!]$ for $m \geq 2$ (for $m = 1$ it is not defined, as $0! = 1! = 1!$), therefore this function is defined for $x > 1$.

In the same manner, $S_*(x) = m$ if $x \in [m!, (m+1)!)$ for $m \geq 1$, i.e. $S_* : [1, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ (while $S : (1, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$).

It is immediate that

$$S(x) = \begin{cases} S_*(x) + 1, & \text{if } x \in (k!, (k+1)!) \quad (k \geq 1) \\ S_*(x), & \text{if } x = (k+1)! \quad (k \geq 1) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, $S_*(x) + 1 \geq S(x) \geq S_*(x)$, and it will be sufficient to study the function $S_*(x)$.

The following simple properties of S_* are immediate:

1° S_* is surjective and an increasing function

2° S_* is continuous for all $x \in [1, \infty) \setminus A$, where $A = \{k!, k \geq 2\}$, and since $\lim_{x \nearrow k!} S_*(x) = k - 1$, $\lim_{x \searrow k!} S_*(x) = k$ ($k \geq 2$), S_* is continuous from the right in $x = k!$ ($k \geq 2$), but it is not continuous from the left.

3° S_* is differentiable on $(1, \infty) \setminus A$, and since $\lim_{x \searrow k!} \frac{S_*(x) - S_*(k!)}{x - k!} = 0$, it has a right-derivative in $A \cup \{1\}$.

4° S_* is Riemann integrable in $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ for all $a < b$.

a) If $[a, b] \subset [k!, (k+1)!]$ ($k \geq 1$), then clearly

$$\int_a^b S_*(x) dx = k(b - a) \quad (4)$$

b) On the other hand, since

$$\int_{k!}^l = \int_{k!}^{(k+1)!} + \int_{(k+1)!}^{(k+2)!} + \dots + \int_{(k+l-k-1)!}^{(k+l-k)!}$$

(where $l > k$ are positive integers), and by

$$\int_{k!}^{(k+1)!} S_*(x) dx = k[(k+1)! - k!] = k^2 \cdot k!, \quad (5)$$

we get

$$\int_{k!}^l S_*(x) dx = k^2 \cdot k! + (k+1)^2(k+1)! + \dots + [k + (l - k - 1)]^2[k + (l - k - 1)!] \quad (6)$$

c) Now, if $a \in [k!, (k+1)!]$, $b \in [l!, (l+1)!]$, by

$$\int_a^b = \int_a^{(k+1)!} + \int_{(k+1)!}^l + \int_l^k$$

and (4), (5), (6), we get:

$$\int_a^b S_*(x) dx = k[(k+1)! - a] + (k+1)^2(k+1)! + \dots + [k+1 + (l-k-2)]^2[k+1 + (l-k-2)]! + l(b-l!) \quad (7)$$

We now prove the following

Theorem 1.

$$S_*(x) \sim \frac{\log x}{\log \log x} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (8)$$

Proof. We need the following

Lemma. Let $x_n > 0$, $y_n > 0$, $\frac{x_n}{y_n} \rightarrow a > 0$ (finite) as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where $x_n, y_n \rightarrow \infty$ ($n \rightarrow \infty$). Then

$$\frac{\log x_n}{\log y_n} \rightarrow 1 \quad (n \rightarrow \infty). \quad (9)$$

Proof. $\log \frac{x_n}{y_n} \rightarrow \log a$, i.e. $\log x_n - \log y_n = \log a + \varepsilon(n)$, with $\varepsilon(n) \rightarrow 0$ ($n \rightarrow \infty$). So

$$\frac{\log x_n}{\log y_n} - 1 = \frac{\log a}{\log y_n} + \frac{\varepsilon(n)}{\log y_n} \rightarrow 0 + 0 \cdot 0 = 0.$$

Lemma 2. a) $\frac{n \log \log n!}{\log n!} \rightarrow 1$;

b) $\frac{\log n!}{\log(n+1)!} \rightarrow 1$;

c) $\frac{\log \log n!}{\log \log(n+1)!} \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (10)

Proof. a) Since $n! \sim Ce^{-n}n^{n+1/2}$ (Stirling's formula), clearly $\log n! \sim n \log n$, so b) follows by $\frac{\log n}{\log(n+1)} \sim 1$ ((9), since $\frac{n}{n+1} \sim 1$). Now c) is a consequence of b) by the Lemma. Again by the Lemma, and $\log n! \sim n \log n$ we get

$$\log \log n! \sim \log(n \log n) = \log n + \log \log n \sim \log n$$

and a) follows.

Now, from the proof of (8), remark that

$$\frac{n \log \log n!}{\log(n+1)!} < \frac{S_*(x) \log \log x}{\log x} < \frac{n \log \log(n+1)!}{\log n!}$$

and the result follows by (10).

Theorem 2. *The series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(S_*(n))^\alpha}$ is convergent for $\alpha > 1$ and divergent for $\alpha \leq 1$.*

Proof. By Theorem 1,

$$A \frac{\log n}{\log \log n} < S_*(n) < B \frac{\log n}{\log \log n}$$

($A, B > 0$) for $n \geq n_0 > 1$, therefore it will be sufficient to study the convergence of

$$\sum_{n \geq n_0}^{\infty} \frac{(\log \log n)^\alpha}{n(\log n)^\alpha}.$$

The function $f(x) = (\log \log x)^\alpha / x(\log x)^\alpha$ has a derivative given by

$$x^2(\log x)^{2\alpha} f'(x) = (\log \log x)^{\alpha-1} (\log x)^{\alpha-1} [1 - (\log \log x)(\log x + \alpha)]$$

implying that $f'(x) < 0$ for all sufficiently large x and all $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. Thus f is strictly decreasing for $x \geq x_0$. By the Cauchy condensation criterion ([2]) we know that $\sum a_n \leftrightarrow \sum 2^n a_{2^n}$ (where $\leftrightarrow$ means that the two series have the same type of convergence) for (a_n) strictly decreasing, $a_n > 0$. Now, with $a_n = (\log \log n)^\alpha / n(\log n)^\alpha$ we have to study $\sum \frac{2^n (\log \log 2^n)^\alpha}{2^n (\log 2^n)^\alpha} \leftrightarrow \sum \left(\frac{\log n + a}{n + b} \right)^\alpha$, where a, b are constants ($a = \log \log 2$, $b = \log 2$). Arguing as above, (b_n) defined by $b_n = \left(\frac{\log n + a}{n + b} \right)^\alpha$ is a strictly positive, strictly decreasing sequence, so again by Cauchy's criterion

$$\sum_{n \geq m_0} b_n \leftrightarrow \sum_{n \geq m_0} \frac{2^n (\log 2^n + a)^\alpha}{(2^n + b)^\alpha} = \sum_{n \geq m_0} \frac{2^n (nb + a)^\alpha}{(2^n + b)^\alpha} = \sum_{n \geq m_0} c_n.$$

Now, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{c_{n+1}}{c_n} = \frac{1}{2^{\alpha-1}}$, by an easy computation, so D'Alembert's criterion proves the theorem for $\alpha \neq 1$. But for $\alpha = 1$ we get the series $\sum \frac{2^n (nb + a)}{2^n + b}$, which is clearly divergent.

References

- [1] J. Sándor, *On certain generalizations of the Smarandache function*, Notes Numb. Th. Discr. Math. 5(1999), No.2, 41-51.
- [2] W. Rudin, *Principles of Mathematical Analysis*, Second ed., Mc Graw-Hill Company, New York, 1964.